

PHYTOCHEMICAL PROFILING, TOTAL FLAVONOID CONTENT AND ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY OF FRUITS EXTRACT OF *HELICTERES ISORA*

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462022

Abstract

The present study was undertaken to investigate the phytochemical profile, total phenolic content, total flavonoid content, and antioxidant activity of the hydroalcoholic fruit extract of *Helicteres isora*. The fruits were extracted using a hydroalcoholic solvent system and the percentage yield of the extract was found to be 6.50% w/w. Preliminary phytochemical screening revealed the presence of flavonoids and carbohydrates, while alkaloids, glycosides, saponins, phenols, proteins, diterpenes, tannins, and sterols were absent. Quantitative estimation showed that the hydroalcoholic extract contained total phenolic content of 0.56 mg/100 mg and total flavonoid content of 0.79 mg/100 mg. Antioxidant activity was evaluated by DPPH free radical scavenging assay using ascorbic acid as standard. The hydroalcoholic extract exhibited concentration-dependent antioxidant activity with percentage inhibition ranging from 25.79% to 56.98% at concentrations of 10–100 µg/mL, whereas ascorbic acid showed inhibition ranging from 40.52% to 89.09%. The IC₅₀ value of the hydroalcoholic extract was found to be 87.14 µg/mL compared to 23.22 µg/mL for ascorbic acid. The observed antioxidant activity may be attributed to the presence of flavonoids and other phytoconstituents in the extract. The results suggest that the fruits of *Helicteres isora* possess significant antioxidant potential and may serve as a promising natural source of bioactive compounds for pharmaceutical and nutraceutical applications.

Keywords

Helicteres isora, Phytochemical screening, Hydroalcoholic extract, Total flavonoid content, Total phenolic content, Antioxidant activity, DPPH assay, IC₅₀ value, Medicinal plants, Free radical scavenging activity.

Introduction

Medicinal plants have been extensively utilized since ancient times as valuable sources of therapeutic agents for the prevention and treatment of various human diseases (Shakya et al., 2016). Plant-derived phytoconstituents such as flavonoids, alkaloids, phenolics, tannins, glycosides, saponins, and terpenoids possess significant biological and pharmacological activities including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antidiabetic, hepatoprotective, and anticancer effects. In recent years, there has been growing scientific interest in the phytochemical investigation of medicinal plants due to their potential role in combating oxidative stress-related disorders and their comparatively safer profile than synthetic drugs (Ansari et al., 2025).

Oxidative stress is caused by the excessive production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and free radicals, which can damage cellular components such as lipids, proteins, and nucleic acids. This oxidative damage is closely associated with the pathogenesis of several chronic diseases including diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular disorders, neurodegenerative diseases, inflammation, aging, and cancer (Galli et al., 2005). Antioxidants play an important role in neutralizing free radicals and protecting biological systems against oxidative damage. Natural antioxidants obtained from medicinal plants are considered highly beneficial because of their effectiveness, safety, and nutritional value (Lushchak et al., 2014).

Helicteres isora, commonly known as Indian Screw Tree, belongs to the family Sterculiaceae (or Malvaceae according to recent classification) and is widely distributed throughout India and Southeast Asian countries. The plant has been traditionally used in Ayurvedic and folk medicine for the treatment of various ailments such as diarrhea, dysentery, colic, diabetes, asthma, wounds, skin disorders, and gastrointestinal disturbances. Different parts of the plant including fruits, bark, roots, and leaves are reported to possess important medicinal properties (Cunningham et al., 2018).

The fruits of *Helicteres isora* are particularly rich in bioactive phytochemicals and are traditionally used for their antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, and hepatoprotective activities. Previous phytochemical studies have reported the presence of flavonoids, tannins, phenolic compounds, steroids, alkaloids, and glycosides in the plant. Among these phytoconstituents, flavonoids are considered important secondary metabolites due to their strong antioxidant potential and ability to scavenge free radicals. Total flavonoid content is often

used as an important parameter for evaluating the antioxidant capacity and therapeutic potential of medicinal plant extracts (Chavre et al., 2024).

Phytochemical profiling is an essential step in identifying the bioactive constituents present in medicinal plants and provides scientific validation for their traditional uses. Qualitative and quantitative phytochemical investigations help in understanding the therapeutic importance of herbal drugs and support the development of plant-based pharmaceutical formulations. Furthermore, the assessment of antioxidant activity through various in vitro methods provides valuable information regarding the free radical scavenging ability of plant extracts (Bhardwaj et al., 2022).

Therefore, the present study was undertaken to evaluate the phytochemical constituents, determine the total flavonoid content, and assess the antioxidant activity of fruit extracts of *Helicteres isora*. The findings of this investigation may provide scientific evidence for the medicinal value of the plant and support its potential application in the development of natural antioxidant formulations and herbal therapeutics.

Material and Methods

Materials

The fruits of *Helicteres isora* were collected and used for the present investigation. Ethanol and distilled water were used for preparation of the hydroalcoholic extract. Various reagents and chemicals utilized for phytochemical screening included Hager's reagent, lead acetate solution, alkaline reagent, ferric chloride, Fehling's solution, gelatin solution, copper acetate solution, and Salkowski reagent. Folin–Ciocalteu reagent and aluminum chloride were used for the estimation of total phenolic and flavonoid content, respectively. DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) and ascorbic acid were used for antioxidant activity studies. All chemicals and solvents used in the study were of analytical grade.

Methods

Extraction by soxhlet extraction process

50 gram of plant materials of *Helicteres Isora* were extracted with hydroalcoholic solvent (Ethanol: water; 75:25) by soxhlet extraction method. The extract was evaporated above their boiling points. Finally, the percentage yields were calculated of the dried extracts (Mukherjee, 2007).

Determination of percentage yield

The extraction yield is evaluate of the solvent's efficiency to extracts bioactive components from the selected natural plant samples and it was defined as quantity of plant extracts recovered in mass after solvent extraction compared with the initial quantity of plant samples. After extraction, yield of the plant extracts obtained were calculated in grams and then converted it into percentage. The percentage yield of extract was calculated by using following formula:

$$\text{Percentage Yield} = \frac{\text{Weight of Extract}}{\text{Weight of Powder drug taken}} \times 100$$

Phytochemical screening

Phytochemical examinations were carried out for all the extracts as per the standard methods (Khandelwal, 2005).

Estimation of total phenolic and flavonoid content

Total phenolic content estimation (TPC)

The total phenolic content of the extract was determined by the modified Folin-Ciocalteu method (Gaur Mishra *et al.*, 2017). 10 mg Gallic acid was dissolved in 10 ml methanol, various aliquots of 10-50µg/ml was prepared in methanol. 10mg of dried extracts of were dissolved in 10 ml methanol and filter. Two ml (1mg/ml) of this solution was used for the estimation of phenol. 2 ml of each extract or standard was mixed with 1 ml of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (previously diluted with distilled water 1:10 v/v) and 1 ml (7.5g/l) of sodium carbonate. The mixture was vortexed for 15s and allowed to stand for 15 min for colour development. The absorbance was measured at 765 nm using a spectrophotometer.

Total flavonoids content estimation (TFC)

Determination of total flavonoids content was based on aluminium chloride method (Gaur Mishra *et al.*, 2017). 10 mg quercetin was dissolved in 10 ml methanol, and various aliquots of 5- 25µg/ml were prepared in methanol. 10mg of dried extracts of were dissolved in 10 ml methanol and filtered. 3 ml (1mg/ml) of this solution was used for the estimation of flavonoid. 1 ml of 2% AlCl₃ methanolic solution was added to 3 ml of extract or standard and allowed to stand for 15 min at room temperature; absorbance was measured at 420 nm.

***In-vitro* antioxidant activity by DPPH free radical scavenging assay**

Antioxidant activity was performed using 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical scavenging assay (Parkhe and Bharti, 2019). Sample (10 mg) was dissolved in methanol (10 mL) to obtain a stock concentration of 1000 µg/mL. The stock solution was further diluted to final concentrations of 10, 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 µg/mL in methanol. The DPPH solution was freshly prepared in MeOH (6mg in 100ml methanol). Then, 1.5 mL of DPPH solution was added to 1.5 mL of sample solution of different concentrations.

An equal volume of DPPH and methanol except sample was used as control. Methanol was used as blank in this method. The mixture was allowed to react at room temperature in the dark. After 15 minutes, the absorbance of the reaction mixture was recorded at 517 nm. Then, Final decrease in absorbance was noted of DPPH with the sample at different concentration. The percentage inhibition (%) was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Calculation of \% Inhibition} = \frac{\text{Control absorbance} - \text{Test absorbance}}{\text{Control absorbance}} \times 100$$

The concentration of plant extract necessary to scavenge 50% of radicals (IC₅₀) was calculated by plotting inhibition percentages against concentrations of sample.

Results and Discussion

The present investigation was carried out to evaluate the phytochemical profile, total phenolic and flavonoid content, and antioxidant activity of the hydroalcoholic extract of *Helicteres isora* fruits. The results obtained from the study indicate that the plant possesses significant phytochemical constituents and appreciable antioxidant potential, supporting its traditional medicinal importance.

The percentage yield of the hydroalcoholic extract was found to be 6.50% w/w, indicating effective extraction of phytoconstituents using the hydroalcoholic solvent system. Hydroalcoholic solvents are widely used in phytochemical investigations because they can efficiently extract both polar and moderately non-polar compounds from plant materials. The obtained yield suggests the presence of a considerable amount of bioactive compounds in the fruits of *Helicteres isora*.

Preliminary phytochemical screening revealed the presence of flavonoids and carbohydrates in the hydroalcoholic extract, while alkaloids, glycosides, saponins, phenols, proteins, diterpenes, tannins, and sterols were absent under the tested conditions. The positive response for flavonoids observed in the lead acetate and alkaline reagent tests indicates that the extract contains flavonoid compounds, which are known for their antioxidant and free radical scavenging activities. Flavonoids are important secondary metabolites that contribute significantly to the therapeutic potential of medicinal plants through their anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, hepatoprotective, and antioxidant properties.

The quantitative estimation of phytoconstituents demonstrated that the hydroalcoholic extract contained total phenolic content of 0.56 mg/100 mg and total flavonoid content of 0.79 mg/100 mg. The comparatively higher flavonoid content observed in the extract may be responsible for its antioxidant activity. Phenolic and flavonoid compounds are well recognized for their ability to donate hydrogen atoms or electrons and neutralize free radicals, thereby protecting biological systems from oxidative damage. The presence of these compounds in *Helicteres isora* fruits supports its potential use as a natural antioxidant source.

The antioxidant activity of the hydroalcoholic extract was evaluated by the DPPH free radical scavenging assay and compared with standard ascorbic acid. The hydroalcoholic extract exhibited concentration-dependent free radical scavenging activity, with percentage inhibition increasing from 25.79% at 10 µg/mL to 56.98% at 100 µg/mL. In comparison, ascorbic acid showed stronger antioxidant activity with inhibition values ranging from 40.52% to 89.09% over the same concentration range. The increase in percentage inhibition with increasing concentration suggests that the antioxidant activity of the extract is dose dependent.

The IC₅₀ value of the hydroalcoholic extract was found to be 87.14 µg/mL, whereas the standard ascorbic acid showed a lower IC₅₀ value of 23.22 µg/mL. Since lower IC₅₀ values indicate stronger antioxidant potential, ascorbic acid exhibited higher antioxidant activity than the plant extract. However, the hydroalcoholic extract still demonstrated appreciable free radical scavenging ability, which may be attributed to the presence of flavonoids and other polyphenolic constituents in the extract.

The antioxidant potential observed in the fruits of *Helicteres isora* may help in protecting cells against oxidative stress-induced damage associated with various chronic diseases such as diabetes, cardiovascular disorders, inflammation, neurodegenerative diseases, and cancer. The

findings of the present study are in agreement with previous reports suggesting that medicinal plants rich in flavonoids and phenolic compounds possess significant antioxidant properties.

Table 1: Results of percentage yield of extract of *Helicteres isora*

S. No.	Extract	Weight of extract	Percentage yield (w/w)
1.	Hydroalcoholic	3.25	6.50%

Table 2: Result of phytochemical screening of extract of *Helicteres isora*

S. No.	Constituents	Hydroalcoholic extract
1.	Alkaloids A) Hager's Test:	-Ve
2.	Glycosides A) Legal's Test:	-Ve
3.	Flavonoids A) Lead acetate Test: B) Alkaline Reagent Test:	+Ve +Ve
4.	Saponins A) Froth Test:	-Ve
5.	Phenol A) Ferric Chloride Test:	-Ve
6.	Proteins A) Xanthoproteic Test:	-Ve
7.	Carbohydrate A) Fehling's Test:	+Ve
8.	Diterpenes A) Copper acetate Test:	-Ve
9.	Tannins A) Gelatin Test	-Ve
10.	Sterols A) Salkowski Test	-Ve

Table 3: Total phenolic and flavonoid content in *Helicteres isora* extract

Extract	Total phenol content mg/100mg	Total flavonoids content mg/100mg
Hydroalcoholic	0.56	0.79

Table 4: DPPH radical scavenging activity of Ascorbic acid

S. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Ascorbic acid (% inhibition)
1	10	40.52
2	20	52.98
3	40	54.74
4	60	72.96
5	80	81.58
6	100	89.09

Table 5: DPPH radical scavenging activity of hydroalcoholic extract of *Helicteres isora*

S. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Hydroalcoholic extract of <i>Helicteres isora</i> (% inhibition)
1	10	25.79
2	20	31.06
3	40	37.37
4	60	40.25
5	80	48.36
6	100	56.98

Figure 1: Graph of % inhibition of Ascorbic acid and hydroalcoholic extract of *Helicteres isora*

Table 6: IC₅₀ value for DPPH assay of Ascorbic acid and hydroalcoholic extract of *Helicteres isora*

S. No	Standard / Plant Extract	IC ₅₀ (µg/mL)
1.	Ascorbic acid	23.22
2.	Hydroalcoholic extract	87.14

Conclusion

The present study demonstrated that the hydroalcoholic fruit extract of *Helicteres isora* contains important phytoconstituents, particularly flavonoids, along with appreciable antioxidant activity. The extract showed significant free radical scavenging potential in the DPPH assay, which may be attributed to the presence of phenolic and flavonoid compounds. The findings support the traditional medicinal use of the plant and suggest that *Helicteres isora* fruits may serve as a potential natural source of antioxidant agents for pharmaceutical and nutraceutical applications.

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